

1 **Ifi27L1/L2 functions in immunologic privilege in the CNS.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We identified subversion of CNS immunologic privilege as a potential mechanism by which metastasis to
8 the CNS is able to occur in humans with cancer. The interferon stimulated genes Ifi2711 and Ifi2712 were
9 isolated as candidate receptors in this process.

10 We sought mechanism(a) of action for suspected or hypothesized immunologic privilege properties for
11 Ifi2711 and Ifi27L2. We employed a set of genomic, proteomic and transcriptomic tools to define precise
12 molecular mechanisms by which immunologic privilege is executed.

13 Immunologic privilege was effected through several mechanisms: those involving self non-self recognition
14 alteration, HLA adaptive immune mechanisms, killer cell processes related to rejection, neuronal, nervous
15 system, brain and CNS-restricted gene expression, transformation and the tumor signature, use of cellular
16 co-receptors, and other processes or mechanisms. Targeted cellular identity changes found in metastasis
17 to the brain involving tailored nuclear factor expression is presented elsewhere.

18 These data demonstrate specificity for Ifi27L1/Ifi27L2 and elucidate multiple mechanisms for its organ
19 system-specific toleragenic function as a major cell surface receptor associated with immunologic privilege
20 in the mammalian or human CNS.
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

1 **Results**

2 I. Ifi27L2 binding partners: PPI proteomic analysis.

3 We identified TMEM168 as a potential co-receptor for this process.

4 TMEM168-binding partners were then identified using STRING.

5
6 II. Ifi27L2 co-regulated genes in the human transcriptome.

7 We identified BLVRA as a potential co-receptor for this process.

8 III. BLVRA-binding partners were then identified using STRING.

9 IV. MICA as a primary mediator of the immunologic privilege mechanism in the human CNS.

10 V. Rgs20

11 VI. MR1 and HMHA1 as potential histocompatibility-associated interaction partners of Ifi27L2 in immunologic privilege

12 VII. LRRC8A
LRRC8C

13 VIII. Class I and II MHC molecules co-regulated with Ifi27L2

14 HLA-B
15 HLA-E
16 HLA-J
17 HLA-C
18 HLA-F
19 HLA-DPA1
20 HLA-DPB1

21 IX. Lynx1 (Ly6/neurotoxin-1) is specifically co-regulated with Ifi27I2.

22 X. A natural killer signature.

23 Cd274
24 Il12a
25 Cd82
26 Cd99b
27 Cd109

28 XI. Interferon genes not co-regulated with Ifi27I2.

Ifi30

XII. Hla genes co-regulated with Ifi27I2.

Hcg4

- 1 XIII. HLA genes not co-regulated with Ifi2712.
2 Hcg4b
3 Hcg9
- 4 XIV. Ifi2711 and TM2D1
5 Scamp3
6 HLA-DPA1
- 7 XV. Ifi27 and Hpcal1
- 8 XVI. Itm2a and Itm2c
9 Ifi2712-specific
- 10 XVII. Igsf8 and Igsf11
11 Ifi2712-specific
- 12 XVIII. PRR16
13 Ifi2712-specific
- 14 XIX. Clec11a, a co-receptor involved in self non-self discrimination.
15 Ifi2712-specific
16 Clec2b was not specific to Ifi2712
17 Ifi30
- 18 XX. Pea15, a CNS-associated proliferation molecule
19 Ifi2712-specific
- 20 XXI. Lesser suggested interaction or affinity between Ifi2712 and stromal antigens Epsti1 and BST2
21 compared to Ifi30.
- 22 XXII. Ly96 and IFI16 as cooperating molecules in execution of CNS organ system-specific protection
23 from inappropriate host immunologic activation.
- 24 XXIII. Other relevant receptors.
25 Tmem184b
26 Ticam2
27 Fam228b
- 28 XXIV. A mechanism involving dynactin.
Dctn1
Dctn2
Dctn3
- XXV. Butyrophilins in CNS immunologic privilege via Ifi27L2.
Btn2a2
Btn3a1
Btn3a3

- 1
2 XXVI. Other potential interaction partners of relevance for a function of Ifi27L2 in the CNS.
3 C6orf1 and C9orf89
4 Robo3
5 Keratins Krt34 and Krt33a
6 Col13a1
- 7 XXVII. CNS-restricted genes
8 NGF and NGFRAP
9 Nrn1
10 Ntm
11 Nav1 and Nav3
12 Nenf
13 Bai2
- 14 XXVIII. Genes associated with transformation in the CNS
15 Nov
16 Nbl1
- 17 XXIX. Genes associated with transformation
18 PSG9
19 Tfpt
20 Lhfp
21 Sdccag8
- 22 XXX. Cell adhesion
23 Integrins
24 Itga3
25 Cadherins
26 CDH11
27 Cdh4
28 Cdh13
- 29 XXXI. Other molecules
30 Dync1h1
31 Dynein-associated
32 Itgb1bp1
33 Stoml1
34 Lxpn
35 Nudcd3 and Nde1
- 36 XXXII. Ifi27L2 co-regulates with oligodendrocyte-restricted genes, but Ifi30 does not.
37 Myelin basic protein MBP
38 Pmp2
39 Pmp22
- 40 XXXIII. Ifi27L2 co-regulates with a stem cell or pluripotency signature.
41 Cd44
42 Cd24
43 Flt family genes
44
45
46
47
48

1 XXXIV. Ifi27l2 does not interact transcriptionally with liver metastasis signature genes or liver-expressed
2 genes.

3 FGA
4 FGB
5 FGA
6 Alb
7 Itih2
8 Leap2

9 XXXV. Ifi27l2 does not co-regulate with Ifi30.

10 XXXVI. Sox11 is modestly co-regulated with Ifi27l2, but Ifi30 is not.

11 XXXVII. PPAR δ is modestly co-regulated with Ifi27l2, but Ifi30 is not.

12 XXXVIII. Nxpe3 and Ifi27l2.

13 XXXIX. Ifi27l2 is co-regulated with TMEM184b and Fam228b: genes co-regulated with TMEM184b and
14 Fam228b.

15 XXXX. Pced1a
16 Ano10

17 XXXXI. Ifi27l2 co-regulates with CERCAM, cerebral cell adhesion molecule, but Ifi30 does not.

18 XXXXII. Ifi30 does not co-regulate with any neuronal, nerve-associated or nervous, or brain-restricted
19 genes in the top 2000 genes (equivalent to 10%) co-regulated across the transcriptome.
20 Two glial genes and MANF were the exception.

21 XXXXIII. Ifi30 is associated with a death signature.
22 MLKL
23 Caspase-1, caspase-7, caspase-8 and caspase-4
24 Tradd
25 Fadd
26 Dap3
27 Pdc10
28 Cideb
Cflar

XXXXIV. Systems biologic analysis of Ifi27L2.

KEGG

Allograft rejection
Antigen processing and presentation
Cell adhesion molecules